

A Simple Deviation Function to Summarize Data in Solvent Mixtures. The Standard Oxidation Potential of the Silver Chloride Electrode in Water-Ethylene Glycol Mixtures

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The data by Kundu *et al* on the standard oxidation potential of the silver chloride electrode in mixtures of water and ethylene glycol have been summarized using the simple deviation function introduced by the present writer. Over the whole range of concentration and temperature range studied the E° -values (molality scale) can be fitted to within ± 1 mV with six constants, of which two can be given theoretical meaning.

RECENTLY, a simple method to summarize thermodynamic data in solvent mixtures was devised¹. In the paper the method is applied to some E_m° -data in water-ethylene glycol mixtures².

The model :

The basis is the zeroth approximation by Guggenheim³. According to this model the number of A-A pairs, B-B and A-B(=B-A) pairs in a mixture of the two components A and B, are given by x_A^2 , x_B^2 and $2x_Ax_B$. Here x_A and x_B are the stoichiometric mole fractions of A and B in the mixtures.

It is now assumed that any property Y can be split into three parts, (y_A) which is a characteristic of solvent A, (y_B) characteristic of solvent B, and (y'_{AB}) characteristic of the mixtures. The following expression is thus obtained

$$Y = y_A x_A^2 + y_B x_B^2 + 2y'_{AB} x_A x_B \quad \dots (1)$$

This homogeneous equation is related to

$$Y = y_A x_A + y_B x_B + y_{AB} x_A x_B \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{by } y'_{AB} = \frac{1}{2}(y_A + y_B + y_{AB}) \quad \dots (3)$$

From plots of Y vs (x_A) or Y vs (x_B), the quantities y_A , y_B and y'_{AB} can be obtained using eqn (3). The use of these equations is illustrated below.

Application :

Instead of the E_m° -values use has been made of the equilibrium constant of the reaction

The equilibrium constant K_m is related to E_m° by

$$\log K_m = nFE_m^\circ / RT \ln 10 \quad \dots (5)$$

Application of eqn (2) to reaction (4) gives

$$\log K_m = \log K_{EG} x + \log K_{H_2O} (1-x) + Bx(1-x) \quad \dots (6)$$

x = the mole fraction of ethylene glycol (EG) in the mixture.

$\log K_{EG} = \log K$ of reaction (4) in pure ethylene glycol in molal units.

$\log K_{H_2O} = \log K$ of reaction (4) in pure water in molal units.

B = deviation function, which generally is assumed to be a function of x , most often expressed as a power series in x , i.e.

$$B = a + bx + cx^2 + \dots \quad \dots (7)$$

At present only $B=0$ and $B=a$ can be given theoretical meaning. For $B=0$, y'_{AB} is the arithmetic average of Y in the two pure solvents. For $B=a$, y'_{AB} is constant and can be computed from eqn (3) provided y_A and y_B are constants. For B being a function of x , the approach is purely empirical, only offering a convenient way of summarizing experimental data.

The simplest way to approach a fitting of eqn (2) is to assume y_A and y_B to be correct and to evaluate B . In the present case it was thus found that eqn (7) could be reduced to

$$B = bx \quad \dots (8)$$

i.e., only one empirical parameter. This implies that the data $\log K(x)$ can be fitted by a third degree polynomial

$$\log K = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + a_3 x^3 \quad \dots (9)$$

where $\log K_{H_2O} = a_0$

$$\log K_{EG} = \sum_0^3 a_i \quad \text{and} \quad \dots (10a-c)$$

$$B = -(a_2 + a_3) - a_3 x$$

By using eqns (10a-c), the constants in eqn (9) can be transformed into the parameters in eqn (2). Values for $\log K$ at various concentrations computed from eqn (2) can then be transformed into E_m° -values using eqn (5).

Results and Discussion

In Table 1, experimental and computed E_m° -values are compared. The first column gives w , the weight per cent of EG in the mixture, then follows

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themselves, who fit E_m^0 for each mixture studied with three constants in the expression

$$E_m^0 = \sum_0^2 a_i (t - 25)^i \quad (t = \text{temperature in degree centigrade})$$

i.e. 21 constants instead of 6 only to fit the temperature dependence. The authors claim the fit to be about ± 0.3 mV. However, to fit five experimental point with three constants leads to a large uncertainty in each constant. For that reason, the approach presented here does not only have the merit of giving a fair description of the concentration and temperature dependence of E_m^0 , it also uses the minimum numbers of parameters to fit the deviations from additivity in the mixtures.

When comparing data from different authors on a certain system the agreement sometimes is rather poor. It is the intention of the present writer to use the approach outlined above to summarize data in the literature and try to give the most reasonable set of parameters, when comparing all available data on each system⁴.

References

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2. U. SEN, K. K. KUNDU and M. N. DAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, 71, 3665.
3. E. A. GUGGENHEIM, "Mixtures", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1952, p. 30.
4. E. HÖGFELDT, to be published.

Note added in proof: Since this paper was written the model has been extended to comprise the general case with B being a function of x (cf eqn 7) with all constants given a simple theoretical meaning. The application of this general approach to the data by Kundu *et al*² will be published elsewhere.